

QSAR based modeling of a new class of RNA polymerase inhibitors

A. K. Srivastava*, Vinay Kumar Pathak, Archana and Meetu Jaiswal

QSAR Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad- 211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : vinay_qsar@rediffmail.com, draksrivastava1@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Quantitative structure-activity relationship studies were performed on a series of RNA-polymerase inhibitors which show activity against *Rifampicin* resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. Physico-chemical parameters together with indicator variable, gave the best model having significant statistical features including cross-validated parameters. Pogliani factor Q and the results of LOO (leave one out) method confirm the reliability and predictability of the proposed models and it may be concluded that larger and polar groups will favour the inhibitory activity (pIC_{50}).

Keywords : RNA-polymerase inhibitors, QSAR, inhibitory activity, physico-chemical parameters.

Introduction

RNA polymerase inhibitors are associated with variety of sigma factors and form RNA polymerase holoenzyme. It is worth mentioning that every molecule of RNA P contains exactly one sigma factor subunit, which works as a prokaryotic transcript initiation factor for binding to promoter sites on DNA.

The RNA P inhibits the *Rifampicin* class of antibacterial agents and they are being presently used clinically. The essential role of the RNA P sigma factor is to regulate expression of bacteriophage inhibitory peptides targeting the sigma factor of *Staphylococcus aureus*, an important pathogen involved in bacteremias.

RNA polymerase^{1,2} (RNA P or RNA pol) is an enzyme that makes a copy of a DNA or RNA template. In chemical terms, RNA P is a nucleotidyl transferase that polymerizes ribonucleotides at 3' end of RNA transcript. A sigma factor (σ factor) is a prokaryotic transcript initiation factor that must be part of RNA P for specific binding to promoter sites on DNA.

The aim of the present work is to perform the quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) studies on the RNA polymerase inhibitory activity against *Rifampicin* and to identify the molecular properties which optimize the activity.

RNA-polymerase inhibitors were synthesized by Francis Arhin and co-researchers³ and in our analysis we have used the inhibitory data as reported by them.

Results and discussion

The RNA polymerase inhibitory activity (pIC_{50}) were converted to negative logarithmic value (pIC_{50}) for QSAR analysis. The correlations were obtained between activity and various structural parameters. The structural parameters such as molar refractivity (MR), molar volume (MV), Parachor (Pc) and electronic like polarizability (Pz) were calculated by ACD Lab Chem Sketch software⁴. These parameters have already been found to be useful in various QSAR studies performed earlier⁵⁻⁸ by our research group.

The compounds of this series with their calculated parameters and biological activities are given in Table 1. Autocorrelation matrix showing correlation among all the physico-chemical parameters is reported in Table 2 and from this table, it was concluded that there is no autocorrelation between structural parameters that were used in bi-parametric regression studies. The aim of the current study is to see whether the physico-chemical parameters can be used for modeling the RNA polymerase inhibitory activity (pIC_{50}) of present set of compounds.

We have used maximum R^2 improvement method for obtaining mono- and bi-parametric models which are discussed below.

Modeling of inhibitory activity (pIC_{50}) using various physico-chemical parameters :

$$pIC_{50} = -0.014 (\pm 0.019) MV + 11.009 \quad (1)$$
$$n = 13, R = 0.448, R^2 = 0.201, R^2_A = 0.128,$$

S.E. = 0.643, $F_{(1,11)} = 2.759$, $Q = 0.6967$

$pIC_{50} = -0.022 (\pm 0.011) MV + 1.966 (\pm 0.90) I + 13.401$ (2)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.873$, $R^2 = 0.763$, $R^2_A = 0.715$, S.E. = 0.367, $F_{(2,10)} = 16.057$, $Q = 2.0790$

$pIC_{50} = -0.043 (\pm 0.075) MR + 11.410$ (3)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.361$, $R^2 = 0.130$, $R^2_A = 0.051$, S.E. = 0.670, $F_{(1,11)} = 1.644$, $Q = 0.5388$

$pIC_{50} = -0.086 (\pm 0.047) MR + 2.136 (\pm 0.972) I + 16.022$ (4)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.863$, $R^2 = 0.744$, $R^2_A = 0.693$, S.E. = 0.381, $F_{(2,10)} = 14.532$, $Q = 2.2651$

$pIC_{50} = -0.004 (\pm 0.008) Pc + 10.082$ (5)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.327$, $R^2 = 0.107$, $R^2_A = 0.026$, S.E. = 0.679, $F_{(1,11)} = 1.320$, $Q = 0.4816$

$pIC_{50} = -0.008 (\pm 0.004) Pc + 2.139 (\pm 1.035) I + 13.865$ (6)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.845$, $R^2 = 0.714$, $R^2_A = 0.657$, S.E. = 0.403, $F_{(2,10)} = 12.482$, $Q = 2.0968$

$pIC_{50} = -0.110 (\pm 0.188) Pz + 11.410$ (7)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.360$, $R^2 = 0.130$, $R^2_A = 0.051$, S.E. = 0.670, $F_{(1,11)} = 1.643$, $Q = 0.5388$

$pIC_{50} = -0.219 (\pm 0.12) Pz + 2.138 (\pm 0.971) I + 16.034$ (8)

$n = 13$, $R = 0.863$, $R^2 = 0.745$, $R^2_A = 0.694$, S.E. = 0.381, $F_{(2,10)} = 14.582$, $Q = 2.2651$

Here and here after "n" is the number of data points, "R" is the correlation coefficient, "R²" is coefficient of determination, "R²_A" is adjusted R², "S.E." is the standard error of estimate, "F" is F ratio, "Q" (Q = R/SE) is quality of fit^{9,10}, data within the parenthesis is in confidence interval at 95% level. The robustness and applicability of the above QSAR equations were further confirmed, using the cross validation technique like leave one out (LOO)^{11,12} method.

Table 1. Inhibitory activity and calculated physico-chemical parameters for the compounds used in the present study

Sr. no.	-R ¹	-R ²	MR	MV	Pc	Pz	I	pIC ₅₀ (Observed)
1.	-CONHPh	-CO ₂ Et	105.87	296.00	799.50	41.97	0	6.429
2.	-CONHPh	-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	110.46	312.90	836.70	43.79	0	6.112
3.	-CONHPh	-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	115.09	329.40	876.50	45.62	0	6.397
4.	-CONHPh		114.95	329.00	904.00	45.57	0	6.084
5.	-CONHPh		112.06	318.80	884.30	44.42	0	6.081
6.	-CONHPh		118.83	335.30	930.30	47.11	1	7.874
7.	-CONHPh	-CO ₂ H	96.39	254.10	717.00	38.21	0	8.269
8.		-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	117.14	336.90	893.40	46.43	0	6.384

9.		-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	108.84	302.40	819.90	43.15	0	6.406
10.		-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	108.84	302.40	819.90	43.15	0	6.105
11.		-CO ₂ ⁱ Pr	113.67	318.60	857.50	45.06	0	6.391
12.			110.20	309.10	869.20	43.68	0	6.376
13.			110.20	309.10	869.20	43.68	0	6.677

Note : I = 1 if () group is present at R² otherwise 0.

Table 2. Correlation matrix showing correlation among various physico-chemical parameters and inhibitory activity

	pIC ₅₀	I	MR	MV	Pc	Pz
pIC ₅₀	1.000					
I	0.419	1.000				
MR	-0.361	0.329	1.000			
MV	-0.448	0.318	0.991	1.000		
Pc	-0.327	0.589	0.955	0.951	1.000	
Pz	-0.360	0.329	0.999	0.991	0.955	1.000

Statistically, all linear models (1, 3, 5, 7) are found insignificant since they contain one or more independent structural parameters whose coefficients are smaller than their confidence intervals and in all these four models F-ratio values are low and therefore such models are not acceptable. The correlation level was found

to improve considerably in models (2, 4, 6, 8) when structural parameters and indicator parameters were used together. In such cases the value of R became higher and standard error of estimate was found to decrease. The coefficients of all the structural parameters have been found to be negative which indicates that less polar and less bulkier groups will favour the inhibitory activity. The indicator I has been assigned a value of 1

(one) when () group is present at -R². The co-efficient of I is positive indicating that this group is beneficial and should be retained at position-R² while designing new drugs in the present series.

We have calculated the inhibitory activity for the compounds used and found that the model 2 is the best

model for estimating pIC_{50} . Also the small residue value clearly confirms the findings. Predicted and residual (difference between the observed biological activities and calculated activities) values for compounds derived from best QSAR model are reported in Table 3. The calculated F-value is greater than F theoretical value [$F_{(2,10)} = 4.10$] for all the significant models. The plot of observed pIC_{50} versus predicted pIC_{50} based on model 2 is shown in graph (Fig. 1) and the predicted R^2 was found to be fairly large.

Table 3. Predicted pIC_{50} and residual values using model 2

Sr. no.	Predicted pIC_{50}	Residual
1.	6.786	-0.358
2.	6.409	-0.297
3.	6.040	0.357
4.	6.049	0.035
5.	6.277	-0.196
6.	7.874	0.000
7.	7.723	0.546
8.	5.643	0.511
9.	6.643	-0.237
10.	6.281	-0.538
11.	6.494	0.101
12.	6.471	-0.117
13.	6.494	0.184

Fig. 1. A plot showing comparison between observed and predicted pIC_{50} values using model 2.

Cross validation :

The cross validation analysis was performed using leave one out (LOO) method, in which one compound is removed from the data set and the activity is correlated using the rest of the data set. The value of cross validated R^2 suggests the acceptability of the proposed models. The R^2_{CV} was found to be very close to the value of R^2 suggesting that model 2 is the best model.

Cross validated parameters¹³ are given in Table 4, PRESS (predictive residual sum of squares) appears to be the most important cross validation parameter accounting for a good estimate of the real predictive error of the models. If its value is less than SSY (sum of squares of response value) then one can say that the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant. It is also well known that if the value of PRESS/SSY is less than 0.4 then the models are said to be statistically significant and are better than chance. In our case, (Table 4) for all models (2, 4, 6, 8) PRESS/SSY is less than 0.4 and the value of PRESS is less than SSY clearly indicating the statistical significance of these models. The values of R^2_{CV} were also fairly high indicating that model 2, 4, 6 and 8 are statistically reliable. However, model 2 is found to be the best.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) :

The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)¹³ is yet another parameter which is used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. We have calculated PE value of all the proposed models and they are reported in Table 4. It is argued that when

- (i) $R < PE$, then correlation is not significant;
- (ii) $R > PE$; several times (at least three times), then correlation is indicated; and if
- (iii) $R > 6PE$, then the correlation is definitely good.

The data presented in Table 4 indicates that in all the cases R is much larger than $6PE$ indicating that they possess high degree of correlation.

Table 4. Calculated cross validation parameters and predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) for the proposed models

Model	Parameter used	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R^2_{CV}	R	$1-R^2$	PE	$6PE$
2	MV, I	1.966	13.401	0.1467	0.8533	0.873	0.237	0.0438	0.2628
4	MR, I	1.454	4.225	0.3441	0.6559	0.863	0.256	0.0473	0.2839
6	Pc, I	1.624	4.055	0.4005	0.5995	0.845	0.286	0.0528	0.3172
8	Pz, I	1.450	4.229	0.3429	0.6571	0.863	0.255	0.0471	0.2828

On the basis of the above discussions following conclusions are drawn :

- (1) Among all the parameters MV is most suitable for modeling inhibitory activity (pIC_{50}) of compounds used in the present study.
- (2) Less polar and less bulky groups should be used in future modeling.

- (3) The group at R² favours the inhibitory activity.

References

1. F. D. Lowy, *N. Eng. J. Med.*, 1998, **339**, 520.
2. (a) C. Freiberg and H. Brotz-Oesterhelt, *Drug Discovery Today*, 2005, **10**, 927; (b) K. S. Murakami and S. A. Darst, *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.*, 2003, **13**, 31.
3. A. Francis, O. Belanger, S. Ciblat, M. Dehbi, D. Delorme, E. Dietrich, D. Dixit, Y. Lafontaine, D. Lehoux, J. Liu, G. A. McKay, G. Moeck, R. Reddy, Y. Rose, R. Srikumar, K. S. E. Tanaka, D. M. Williams, P. Gros, J. Pellitier, T. R. Parr and A. R. Far, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **14**, 5812.
4. www.acdlabs.com, Chem Sketch program of ACD Labs Software.
5. A. K. Srivastava, Archana and M. Jaiswal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 260.
6. A. K. Srivastava and A. Verma, *Oxidation Commun.*, 2006, **29**, 8.
7. A. K. Srivastava, Abha, A. Khan and Archana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 850.
8. A. K. Srivastava and A. Verma, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **9**, 571.
9. L. Pogliani, *Aminoacids*, 1994, **6**, 141.
10. L. Pogliani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 18065.
11. R. D. Cramer (III), J. D. Bunce and D. E. Petterson, *Quant. Struct. Act. Relat.*, 1988, **7**, 18.
12. B. L. Podlogar and D. M. Ferguson, *Drug. Des. Discov.*, 2000, **4**, 17.
13. S. Chatterjee, A. S. Hadi and B. Price, "Regression Analysis by Example", 3rd ed., Wiley VCH, New York, 2000.